

Factoring of the Smarandache Cubic Product Sequence,
by Micha Fleuren

SmCubProd(1): 2
PRIME!

SmCubProd(2): 9
3²

SmCubProd(3): 217
7.31

SmCubProd(4): 13825
5².7.79

SmCubProd(5): 1728001
11².14281

SmCubProd(6): 373248001
7.103.487.1063

SmCubProd(7): 128024064001
71².25396561

SmCubProd(8): 65548320768001
37.61.103.163.661.2617

SmCubProd(9): 47784725839872001
19.71.269.367.3067.116989

SmCubProd(10): 47784725839872000001
11.151.329891.87206528551

SmCubProd(11): 63601470092869632000001
1051.39916801.1516033189651

SmCubProd(12): 109903340320478724096000001
13².283.2834329.3011791.269192317

SmCubProd(13): 241457638684091756838912000001
83.415651.1425217.65456203.75024347

SmCubProd(14): 662559760549147780765974528000001
23.73.1627.4918357.3790360487.13010267983

SmCubProd(15): 2236139191853373760085164032000000001
59.479.853.1297.46271341.1545646643053897261

SmCubProd(16): 9159226129831418921308831875072000000001
17.61.137.139.800221.1059511.15467077.35368854602353

SmCubProd(17): 44999277975861761160390291002228736000000001
79.661.537913.1000357.1601437297538567272123897519

SmCubProd(18): 262435789155225791087396177124997988352000000001
19.23.29.61.67.47977.108843433.123610951.7849585443797104561

SmCubProd(19): 1800047077815693701068450378900361202106368000000001
71.634651.135653893.1713311273363831.171878680928827825207

SmCubProd(20): 1440037662252554960854760303120288961685094400000000001
2287.24379.20639383.117876683047.19261640493919.5511551997380323

SmCubProd(21):
13336188790120911492475935167196996074165659238400000000001

43.439429.2703875815783.11322991339735897207.230529574179983574343

SmCubProd(22):
142003738237207465571883757660313614197715939570483200000000001

23.79^2.103.199.521.6069482787988153.93799610095769647.162718531806079452
1

SmCubProd(23):

17277594831321032336131096794530357439436098367540690944000000000001

47^279.229.8971.15053083131671041.148139754736864591.21611606820489445915
879

SmCubProd(24):

238845470948181951014676282087587661242764623832882511609856000000000001

163.811.589111.765041185860961084291.400891274547717727219213817064009908
2957

SmCubProd(25):

373196048356534298460431690761855720691819724738878924390400000000000000
001

401.8905787442426949460509.38681321803817920159601.2701587462801221828102
6318389

SmCubProd(26):

6559293745914446829740547396830376146879423482010535975085670400000000000
0000001

1697.2039866093.237649652991517758152033.79732685971771022769306300247590
392147593957

SmCubProd(27):

1291065788008340569497831944118122936990276923964133795976112504832000000
000000000001

31.239318943976768064623.10888869450418352160768000001.159818411711295723
45220005880127377

SmCubProd(28):

2834147617835909218161640683728103471281055903486066508926762170607206400
0000000000000001

29.126859.488197.218404415623.10513391193507374500051862069.6872327382164
888882533505084139255169

SmCubProd(29):

6912202625139998992174425463544471556107367243012167608621480257893915688
96000000000000000001

7489.14557.218568437.2778942057555023489.186080472073787611549.5609872756
3904407543220697654183745141

SmCubProd(30):

1866294708787799727887094875157007320148989155613285254327799669631357236
0192000000000000000001

31.12421.82561.1080941.320860064107321.7719068319927551.21928275752950120
1975281187637819276831827680867081

SmCubProd(31):

5559878566949734169348444342580240507455853593487538101167947995798776341
8247987200000000000000000001

241.257.26863.95101.3038779.205486503091.110714485281307653167.5082632174
6155575059538440981830616083367520490117

SmCubProd(32):

1821861008818088892612098242176693209483134105513996484990713199263343031
689150044569600000000000000000000000001

2281.652931.3468499.61146083.2889419049474073777.199619020635225828789820
03150054125254566219063937564260039281499

SmCubProd(33):

6547221907389560533800974529103823869195390349856491681111260241926758529
812985151697715200000000000000000000001

67.457.1327.50989.175433.143446529.651785107.101002716748738111.190756707
658221269804482185897059181232427011258035431061037

SmCubProd(34)*

2573320098480395041620513502891896693354855622310759549034396972548689317
25576956840232699822080000000000000000000001
1033.67411.22794382498141.

c95:

1621193632032688210352456555653135797268317827008250886922129432460793461
8708475827415922662047

SmCubProd(35):

1103310992223469374094795164364900707275894348065738156648497701980250544
773411202452497700487168000000000000000000000001

137.379.17839.18367.61098469.340825649.364853011.174601438051.32731815563
800396289317.1493588605839364977747610330656874957047524118667

SmCubProd(36):

5147607765317818711776676318860880739866412670335507943659230878359056941
694827306162373271392931020800000000000000000000001

37.83.643.739.1483.52237.165202043.669043459524628666916941.4119847097654
015008301075211522196105497276114507428914932929938787238994711

SmCubProd(37)*

2607417761366434712076239855792601921164534009905044838701710216815213112
6766808753904269331586613499658240000000000000000000000001
62909013768204870177696097.

c104:

4144744298446245142965128838417812278446277837061104724503992598233668088
3547023457252166813561236470433

SmCubProd(38):

1430742274016990055210474333670516526181403101915096203892402430170843739
1879483299442350667628206559532469452800000000000000000000001

14029308060317546154181.37280713718589679646221.2735526583816145583533735
06071127403199540399874192973440773009599175173339925708800000001

SmCubProd(39)*

8487020095241383308503012699900136981655465060250159171869341975530427976
4889906983962079925303758490490655547064320000000000000000000000001
79.157.57554485363.146102648914939.30705821478100704367.

c91:

2650150276423157600353382819962960383863063369323356889738335001456535953
925714029574522293

SmCubProd(40):
5431692860954485317441928127936087668259497638560101869996378864339473904
95295404697357311521944054339140195501211648000000000000000000000000000001

41.59.61.277.1201.217823.16558103.142410167827.2370686450613664429.908693
2330127860515264189191721320326318252800341900148086127189164230233553840
161965138341

SmCubProd(41)*
3743577036698440825634151285054830981841128367472007809820204277091408810
03262545871465632674039061691078814141390079918080000000000000000000000000
001

463.25876717.14783665201.26902587937.48417098112776888337918667.
c93:
1622638113255873087996782579039650944932530542466941540272382254672496191
43657774300654853489

SmCubProd(42):
2773541354949140838895830004071423177826455184892661146139592944811482959
17697154985251457935542060025686471821073082409707110400000000000000000000
00000001

43.547.2521.70552493296669.1384892627921059948917925685197.83102759750913
5958568123209119581.1243840543286992983827847320149339.463124113000222170
026612414799459103

SmCubProd(43):
2205159525079413406780907561337066425994479723852608097461206162631265756
352834770141238766608114256646225431507805756314858322657280000000000000000
000000000000001

59.4111.17939.21154320865805720609.2360257878529126150147.269834416651052
6940628578689.37617195047178378579875053892698814131796339915747472782238
3994565705679862943653

SmCubProd(44):
1878443089843647516432248297049366664319137607966605681741353857575817421
89159877059711283094745604838152067157560925545924891357237739520000000000
000000000000000001

84349.694763.9245226412016162109253.4195392584036906151831661.41385205325
7739876455072359.59815670246240613300438042249879673.33383446940555668514
3329600297515753377494033

SmCubProd(45)*
1711731265620023799348886260686235372860814145259569427486808702715963625
69871937970661906720086932408766071197327393403724057249282890137600000000
00000000000000000001

293.20749.138571.494241439.516423571.19789544034049.
c126:
4022698110545767418131860382356272501043152505977540474643644830366784810
44432340230997876735644686603169962575109850806321743